

INDI Fresenius Kabi Research Symposium 2024 Abstract

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Title: A preliminary review of fertility and pregnancy supplements notified to the Food Safety Authority of Ireland in 2024.

Background: Adequate nutrition is essential to meet the demands of the developing foetus^(1, 2). To prevent neural tube defects, folic acid supplementation is recommended before and up to 12 weeks of pregnancy⁽³⁾. Other nutrients such as omega-3 and zinc are associated with improving fertility⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾.

Aim and Objectives: This study aimed to: (1) investigate the number of fertility and pregnancy supplements notified to the FSAI in 2024, as required under S.I.No.506/2007 and (2) identify the nutrients and other substances present in these products.

Research Design: Product data were extracted from the FSAI Food Notification System for Food Supplements (FS) submitted between January 1st and December 31st 2024. Based on database field 'product name', the key search terms were: "fertility", "conception", "conceive", "reproduction", "pregnancy", "lactation", "postpartum", "mother", "prenatal" and "breastfeeding". Information on label including product/brand name, ingredient list and nutritional information were extracted for the analysis. Duplicates and illegible labels were excluded. Frequency analysis was conducted using SPSS (Version 29.0.01).

Results: Preliminary results suggest that 38 FS were marketed as fertility (*n*14), pregnancy (*n*22) or both (*n*2). Approximately 92% contained folic acid (*n*35) and 21% contained omega-3 (*n*8). Maca root (*leidium meyenii*) was the most common plant botanical found in these FS (*n*6).

Conclusion: This study showed that pregnancy supplements were more frequently notified than fertility supplements to the FSAI in 2024. Future work is required to assess the nutrient levels in these FS to ensure their safety on the Irish market.

Word count: 243

Reference:

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